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Correlation Between Organizational Culture And Teachers' Job Commitment In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated correlation between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary school in Anambra State, Nigeria. Four research questions guided the study, and five null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significant. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of 7181 respondents which comprised 266 principals 6915 teachers in all the Public Secondary Schools in the six Education Zones in the State as recorded by the Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC, 2023), Awka. The sample size was 756 respondents comprising 66 principals and 690 teachers randomly drawn from the population. This study adopted stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Instruments for data collection were two questionnaires structured by the researcher titled "Organizational Culture Questionnaire' (OCQ)" and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire' (TJCQ)". The instruments were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistics to determine the reliability, and the average reliability coefficient showed a value of 0.80 for Organizational Culture Questionnaire (OCQ) and 0.88 for Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire which were considered adequate for the study. The questionnaires were administered by the researcher with the help of six briefed research-assistants by direct contact and collected on the spot. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions, Hypotheses were tested using test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. After analyzing the data of the study, it was discovered that a moderate positive (r value of 0.57) and significant relationship existed between clan culture and teachers' job commitment and that a strong positive (r value of 0.89) and significant relationship existed between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Clan Oriented Culture, Adhocracy Oriented Culture, Hierarchy Oriented Culture, Market Oriented Culture, Teachers' Job Commitment

INTRODUCTION

Education is an inevitable tool for sustainable development and a vehicle for advancing knowledge. Education as a tool for building a united independent, wealthy and egalitarian society that can maintain its tradition and values is a social process facilitated through the instrumentality of the school (Kaerner et al., 2020). Omemu (2018), was of the view that development of any nation is primarily dependent on the education system available in the country. Accordingly, Joshua and Ifedayo (2015:pg 6), noted that teachers promote quality education from the domain of teaching and learning through creative ideas, participation and cooperative learning, research, analysis and critical thinking, problem solving, innovation and encouragement of creative and divergent thinking.

Teacher's job commitment in itself has been a subject considered by both teachers and administrators as an important element in a successful school organization. It is an overall feeling about one's job or career in terms of specific facets, and it can be related to specific outcomes. With teachers, commitment in their career may have strong implications for student learning. Teachers' job commitment refers to an individual's attraction and attachment to the work and the organization (Oforgbu, 2014). It refers to the socio-psychological bonding of an individual to his group or organization, its goals and values or to his occupation and profession.

Organizational culture is the rules, values, beliefs, and philosophy that dictate team members' behavior in a company. Organizational culture refers to the beliefs and values that have existed in an organization for a long time (Cameron, 2017). It is a set of values that help people in an organization understand which actions are considered acceptable and which are considered unacceptable (Cameron, 2017). Organizational culture is a system of shared assumptions, values and beliefs that governs how people behave in organization. It provides boundaries and guidelines that help members of the organization know the correct way to perform their jobs. The unique culture of an organization creates a distinct atmosphere that is felt by the people who are part of the group and this atmosphere, is known as the culture of an organization (Okorie, 2014). These are specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in the organization and that control the way they interact with one another and with stakeholders outside the organization. Organizational culture stands as the center from which all other factors of human resource management derive (Anas, 2016). An organization can make several efforts to improve the performance of its members, such as by forming a strong organizational culture and commitment and creating job commitment for its members (Kasmir, 2019). Organizational culture is the beliefs, values, rituals and symbols that govern the operating style of the people within an institution. In the view of Ng'ang'a and Nyongesa (2017), it is the specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in an organization and that control the way they interact with each other and with stakeholder outside the organization.

Clan culture is the type of organizational culture in which shared values, common goals, collectivity and mutual help are emphasized. Clan culture brings in a very harmonious workplace in which there is a lot of communication at the personal level and the whole ambience is that of an extended family (Chennatuserry *et al.*, 2022). Clan culture is people-focused in the sense that the organization feels like one big happy family. This is a highly collaborative work environment where every individual is valued and communication is a top priority. Clan culture is often paired with a horizontal structure, which helps to break down barriers between the school and teachers and encourage mentorship opportunities. Organizational cultures based on the clan concept are focused on a supportive work environment (Richardet.al 2014). Teachers are treated like family and the organization's interest supersedes the individual interests. In addition, the commitment of organizational members is ensured through participation (Brown, 2016).

Adhocracy cultures are rooted in innovation. A flat organizational structure provided by the Adhocracy culture, allows teachers to communicate more directly with one another and may speed up decision making. Igwe (2016) argued that adhocracy cultures value individuality in the sense that teachers are encouraged to think creatively and bring their ideas to the table. Migdadi etal (2017) stated that Adhocracy type of culture promotes adaptability, versatility, and ingenuity in schools to cope with complexity, ambiguity, and knowledge overload. It is a term used in organizational studies to describe a type of organization where decision-making is distributed throughout the organization, rather than being centralized in a few individuals or groups. Thus, because this type of organizational culture falls within the external focus and differentiation category, new ideas need to be tied to organizational growth and success. This culture reflects values around change, entrepreneurialism, excitement, and dynamism, and there is an acceptance of experimentation, innovation, risk, challenge, being on the leading edge, and creativity (Hellriegel, et.al 2014). They further argued that this organizational culture type reacts quickly to change, and also creates it because individual initiative, flexibility and freedom promoting growth are encouraged and rewarded. Effectiveness within this organizational culture type means providing new and unique products and rapid growth.

Hierarchy oriented culture also known as bureaucratic culture is a type of organizational culture that emphasizes formal rules, procedures, and a clearly defined chain of command. It forms around values of power and control, clear delineations of responsibility and authority, and high degrees of

systematizing and formality (Lok et al., 2015). This type of culture values rules, hierarchical coordination, formalization and standard operating procedures with the long term concerns being efficiency, predictability and stability (Hellriegel, Slocum & Woodman, 2014). Administrators within the hierarchy oriented organization are good coordinators, organizers and enforcers of rules and procedures that are clearly defined (Cameron & Quinn, 2015).

Market oriented culture refers to a culture profile of an organization that focuses on external maintenance with a need for stability and control. Narver and Slater (2018), defined market- oriented culture as composed of customer orientation, competitor orientation and inter- departmental collaboration. They also viewed this as a group culture aimed at improving the organization's performance through taking actions that aim at gaining customer value. The Narver and Slater definition can be related to the school concept that emphasizes target students, students' orientation, co-ordinated publicizing effort and mutually profitable exchange. Market culture is a group culture designed to create higher students value by executing the required actions with the most efficient and effective means available, thereby maintaining a high level of organization commitment (Narver & Slater, 2018).

Furthermore, teachers' job commitment represents one of the most complex areas facing today's school administrators when it comes to managing the school. A committed teacher would be psychologically balanced and this would spur higher performance, higher morale, effective performance and productivity among teachers toward achieving the school objectives. Thus, this study seeks to examine the correlation between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State. It is this gap in knowledge that this study has filled.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the crucial role teachers play in shaping the future of students and society, there is a growing concern about their level of job commitment in Nigeria especially in Anambra State public secondary schools. Reports of teacher absenteeism, lateness, and lack of enthusiasm for teaching duties have raised concerns about the impact on student learning outcomes and their academics. The problem is further compounded by factors such as inadequate facilities, poor remuneration, poor organizational culture and lack of motivation, which may contribute to low job commitment among teachers.

Additionally, it is perceived that in most public secondary schools in Anambra State that, teachers' job commitment is particularly pressing issue, as teacher turnover rates are high and many teachers lack the necessary training and support to be effective in their roles in the organization they work. This has led to concerns about the quality of education in the region and the ability of students to reach their full potential. This is why the researcher deem it necessary to investigate organizational culture as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the correlation between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State, Nigeria.
2. examine the relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra, State Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the correlation between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State, Nigeria?
2. What is the correlation between adhocracy culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary School in Anambra State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study

- 1) There is no significant relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary school in Anambra state, Nigeria.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary school in Anambra State Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Anambra State which is one of the 36 States in Nigeria. The population of the study is 7,181 respondents comprised 266 principals 6915 teachers in the six education zones in Anambra State. The sample size is 7181 respondents comprising 66 principals and 690 teachers as respondents in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Two structured instruments by the researcher was used for data collection. The first instrument is titled “Organizational Culture Questionnaire’ (OCQ)” and the second instrument is titled Teachers’ Job Commitment Questionnaire’ (TJCQ)”. The face and construct validation of the instruments were established by three experts; two in educational management and one in Measurement and Evaluation. All three experts are lecturers in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. On the other hand, construct validation was conducted by the use of exploratory factor analysis through Principal Component Analysis, measure of sampling adequacy was obtained as 0.881; which is high to conduct the Principal Component Analysis. This reliability yielded coefficients of 0.85 for Clan Oriented Culture, 0.81 for Adhocracy Oriented Culture, 0.76 for Hierarchy Oriented Culture, 0.75 for Market Oriented Culture. The average reliability coefficient showed a value of 0.80 for Organizational Culture Questionnaire (OCQ) and 0.88 for Teachers’ Job Commitment Questionnaire. Direct method was used to administer the instruments to respondents by the researcher with the help of six research assistants who were briefed on how to administer and retrieve the instruments on respondent in a one-day consultative meeting during which the researcher acquainted them with the purpose of the study and how to exhibit good human relation during data collection.

It was on the spot administration and collection of the instrument where the researcher and research assistant waited for the respondents to fill the Questionnaires and retrieved them immediately. A follow up visit was done to retrieve from those who were not disposed to fill theirs immediately. 7181 copies of questionnaire were distributed by the researcher and her six briefed research assistants. While 529 copies of questionnaire were collected which represented about 70% return and 30% loss, which was a high return rate of the instruments. The research questions were answered using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient while hypotheses was tested at .05 level of significance using test of significance of Pearson product moment correlation, in answering the research questions, the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the interpretation of correlation coefficient was based on Schober et al (2018) as shown:

±0.00 to 0.09	=	Negligible Correlation
±0.10 to 0.39	=	Weak Correlation
±0.40 to 0.69	=	Moderate relationship
±0.70 to 0.89	=	Strong relationship
±0.90 to 1.00	=	Very strong relationship

The null hypotheses was tested at .05 level of significance and the decision rule is if the *P*-value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), do not reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative. If the *P*-value is greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

		Clan oriented culture	Teachers' job commitment	Remark
Clan oriented culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.57**	Moderate positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	529	529	
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.57**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	529	529	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Analysis from Table 1 showed that there is a moderate positive correlation between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is as a result of the 'r' being positive with the value $r = 0.57^{**}$ and $N=529$. Thus, the study concluded that there exists a moderate positive correlation between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

		Adhocracy oriented culture	Teachers' job commitment	Remark
Adhocracy oriented culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.89**	Strong positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	529	529	
teachers' job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.89**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	529	529	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Analysis from Table 2 showed that there is a strong positive correlation between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is as a result of the 'r' being positive with the value $r = 0.89^{**}$ and $N=529$. Thus, the study concluded that there exists a strong positive correlation between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significance relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 3: Test of significance of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in in public secondary schools in Anambra State

		Clan oriented culture	Teachers' job commitment	Decision
Clan oriented culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.57**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	529	529	
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.57**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	529	529	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 5 above showed a significant relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.52^{**}$.N = 529 and p-value =0.00 .Since p-value 0.00 is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis and do not reject alternative hypothesis that there is significance relationship between clan oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis Two: There is no significance relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson correlation analysis on the relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

		adhocracy oriented culture	teachers' job commitment	Decision
Adhocracy oriented culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.89**	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	529	529	
Teachers' job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.89**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	529	529	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 6 above showed a significant relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.89^{**}$.N = 529 and p-value =0.00 .Since p-value 0.00 is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis and do not reject alternative hypothesis that there is significance relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State .

DISCUSSION

The finding from the study showed a moderate positive and significant relationship between clan culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. . This finding is in agreement with Adonu (2017) whose finding showed that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The study

further revealed that clan organizational culture has a friendly, collaborative culture and can be compared to a large family, where people have a lot in common; very high bonds of loyalty, tradition and commonality generally form.

The findings from the study showed a strong positive and significant relationship between adhocracy oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is in agreement with Igwe (2016) whose study indicated that when adhocracy organizational culture is in practiced the institutions reacts quickly to change, and also creates it because of individual initiative, flexibility and freedom promoting growth are encouraged and rewarded.

The findings of the study showed a weak positive and significant relationship between hierarchical oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is in line with Akpan and Eze (2017) who revealed that hierarchy oriented culture was the dominant culture in the tertiary institutions than adhocracy culture.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study showed a moderate positive and significant relationship between clan culture, a strong positive and significant relationship between adhocracy oriented culture, a weak positive and significant relationship between hierarchical oriented culture, a moderate positive and significant relationship between market culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the above findings it was concluded that clan, adhocracy and market culture are people focused while hierarchy cultures adhered to the traditional corporate structure. They focused on internal organization by way of a clear chain of command and multiple management ranks that separated teachers and leadership, hence the weak positive and significant relationship between hierarchical oriented culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the study findings:

- 1) Principals as school administrators should be encouraged by State Education Board to practice clan culture by building relationship trust in the organization which builds the culture for inclusion and innovation.
- 2) There should maintenance of adhocracy oriented culture by school principals' for promoting growth and encouraging personal initiatives among teachers in Public Secondary School in Anambra State Nigeria.

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